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D1.2- Data Management Plan

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Lead author	Emanuel Marzini (Trust-IT)
Contributors	Maria Giuffrida, Paolo Lombardi, Michele Nannipieri (Trust-IT)
Peer Reviewer	Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)
Quality Officer	Sten-Erik Björling (ICF)
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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PMB	Project Management Board
The Consortium / Project Partners	All the Project Partners, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + COMMpla + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TWG	Technical Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Data management; privacy; community building; GDPR; FAIR.

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

This document describes the main data management aspects of digiNEB.eu, including relevant processes and procedures to handle personal data, in compliance with the GDPR.

digiNEB.eu (“Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative”) runs from 1st October 2022 until 30th September 2024, with the central scope of fostering digital solutions that will boost the growing New European Bauhaus (NEB) movement. digiNEB.eu bridges the digital and NEB communities and raises awareness around EU digital solutions for all NEB stakeholders, establishing a pan-European digital ecosystem. With its lean action plan, digiNEB.eu enables Europe’s Green Deal ambition in designing and building greener and more inclusive living spaces for a better quality of life.

This “Data Management Plan”, formally issued at the end of month 4 of the Project but reflecting actions carried out since onset of all project activities, describes the posture that will be maintained, with support from all Project Partners, with respect to the data management procedures and processes, including but not limiting to: handling of personal data, data repository management, particularly concerning sharing and preservation of the data, and Ethics which will be also treated in the Ethics report D1.3 due in month 12.

The document indicates the main datasets expected to be acquired or generated during the course of the project.

This is a living document, given that the procedures and processes defined therein may be subject to modification or refinement. In particular, should new repositories provided by any Partner of the consortium be added to or substitute, for valid reasons, the ones already in use, the present document will be updated accordingly. If needed, these changes will be introduced as revisions of the present version and added to the project’s Document Repository.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope

This “Data Management Plan”, formally issued at the end of Month 4 of the Project, but reflecting actions carried out since onset of all project activities, describes the posture that will be maintained, with support from all Project Partners, in data management, particularly with respect to the following aspects:

- The overall **amount and typology** of data the Project will generate, particularly concerning personal data;
- How the project will ensure that data is well organised and adequately documented (data **processes** and procedures);
- Data storage and back-up during the lifetime of the Project (**data repository** management);
- Distribution of **responsibilities** for looking after data during and after the project and needed resources;
- Data **preservation** and availability for other usages (if appropriate) over the long term;
- **Ethical and legal compliance** of the data (this will be also treated in the Ethics report D1.3 due in Month 12, i.e. August 2023).

Any changes that will need to be made to the processes or procedures identified therein, or any additional risks and mitigation actions as they emerge during the course of the project, will call for a revision of this Version 1.0 of the document.

1.2. Structure of the document

The structure of the document is as follows:

Section 2 “Data Summary” indicates the background reasons and specific goals for data creation and data management in digiNEB.eu. An overall description of the main datasets generated and managed by digiNEB.eu is provided.

Section 3 “Processes & procedures” describes the main roles, responsibilities and practice around data management by the digiNEB.eu Consortium.

Section 4 “Data protection, FAIR principles, and ethical issues” provides practical detail adopted around these aspects by the digiNEB.eu Consortium.

Section 5 “Allocation of resources for data management” provides a rationale and a first estimate of the resources involved with data management in this project.

Section 6 “Conclusions”, Sec. 7 “References”, and Annex 1 “Data Processing Agreement (DPA)” complete the document.

This basic structure will be maintained for possible further iterations of this document.

1.3. Relation with other project deliverables

The following deliverables of digiNEB.eu are related to this document:

- D1.1 “Project Handbook” (V1.0 published in December 2022) /1/
- D1.3 “Ethics Report, Y1” (Expected to be published in M12, i.e. August 2023)
- D1.4 “Ethics Report, Y2” (Expected to be published in M24, i.e. August 2024)

2. Data summary

2.1. Scope and perimeter

To effectively achieve the project goals (see digiNEB.eu Grant Agreement /2/), particularly dissemination and exploitation of the project results, digiNEB.eu will collect and manage different types of data.

The need for data collection is directly arising from the 4 main project objectives, and related quantitative targets, that are:

1. Manage & map a Research & Industry portfolio (Main outputs: 500+ NEB projects mapped and part of the digital Observatory, 8 webinars among NEB projects and stakeholders.).
2. Bringing together both demand and supply side of the NEB industry (Main outputs: digiNEB.eu Toolkit online with 250+ solutions, tools and services addressing the specific needs of all stakeholders, 25 open licences with existing projects).
3. Promoting European excellence in New European Bauhaus thanks to a multistakeholder dialogue and synergies development (Main outputs: 4 sector-specific TWGs, 16 multi-stakeholder workshops, 2 Gap & landscape analysis reports, 1 NEB Roadmap, a profiled and engaged community of 3000+ users.)
4. Stimulating mutual learning and knowledge transfer by making use of EU digital capacities (Main outputs: A continuously updated user-centred platform featuring training services and user forum functionalities delivered in 3 progressive iterations, 1000+ envisaged trained users).

Datasets will be collected through, amongst other ways, desktop research, one-on-one and one-on-many interviews, workshops and other events. In all cases, datasets (intended as collections of structured information) will be created or incremented. Data collected will also include project deliverables, dissemination material, and training materials.

2.2. Main datasets to be generated and managed by digiNEB.eu

The list of the main datasets created and managed by digiNEB.eu is indicated in the table below.

Should any more dataset be created in the future, an update of this table and a new release of the document will be provided.

ID	Dataset	Dataset format	Gathered information	Personal data? (Y/N)	Ethical issues? (Y/N)	Dissemination level	Consent gathered	Notes
#1	Community DB - User credentials to www.digineb.eu	Drupal database representation	Name, surname, email, Organisation, Organisation type	Y	N	website	Privacy form. Cookies consent. Website terms of use.	The official “digiNEB.eu community” resides in this database, which includes proof of the privacy consent.
#2	Digital toolkit Solutions (on www.digineb.eu)	Drupal database representation	Information about the tools published in the Toolkit, including contact.	Y	N	website	Privacy form. Cookies consent. Website terms of use.	Personal contact point may be included
#3	Success stories (on www.digineb.eu)	Drupal database representation	Information about the success stories published in the Observatory, including contact person.	Y	N	website	Privacy form. Cookies consent. Website terms of use.	Personal contact point may be included
#4	Early adopters (on www.digineb.eu)	Drupal database representation	Information about the digiNEB.eu Early Adopters published on the website, included contact. User personal information (name, surname, email)	Y	N	website	Privacy form. Cookies consent. Website terms of use. Consent form to photo/video completed.	
#5	TWG discussions (on observatory.digineb.eu)	Flarum database representation	User personal position about a topic discussed.	Y	Y	website, landscape analysis, report, publication	Waiver form on content provided becoming public	Personal contact point may be included. Although the TWGs are moderated, personal opinions implying ethical issues may occasionally be involved in the discussions
#6	Publications (deliverables, milestone reports, specifications, etc.)	pdf	Author information, (name, affiliation)	N	N	website, ZENODO	Waiver form on content provided becoming public	unique DOI generated by ZENODO

ID	Dataset	Dataset format	Gathered information	Personal data? (Y/N)	Ethical issues? (Y/N)	Dissemination level	Consent gathered	Notes
#7	Webinars, teleconference recordings	video	User personal information registered to an event (name, surname, email)	Y	N	internal use - private	Privacy form. Consent form to photo/video completed.	In some cases, recorded information may be processed by the Zoom video-conference system. Despite being a US-based provider, Zoom complies with GDPR requirements, as per their policy, available here
#8	Events	csv/excel, pdf	User personal information registered to an event (name, surname, email)	Y	N	website	Privacy form. Consent form to photo/video completed.	
#9	Events video footage	video	User behaviour during an event	N	N	website, Youtube, social network	Consent form to photo/video completed	
#10	Live Surveys (mentimeter, Sli.do or similar) at workshops/webinar/f2f meetings	csv/excel, pdf, report	User personal information as a voter (name, surname, email)	Y	N	website, publication, deliverables (only anonymous data)	Privacy form	Data anonymised before publication
#11	Workshop materials	pdf, csv, video		Y	Y	website		
#12	User GDPR consents	MySQL database representation	Drupal ID of user in the website, consents given/rejected	Y	N	Trust-IT servers	Privacy form. Cookies consent. Website terms of use.	Provided by Trust PPG-Tool and stored internally to be GDPR compliant

Table 1 - List of dataset managed by digiNEB.eu

3. Processes and procedures

3.1. Data Controller and Data Processors

As per the Grant Agreement (Task 1.3 “Ethics, data management, and privacy”), in agreement with the GDPR /3/ and as reflected in the digiNEB.eu privacy statement, published [here](#) on the website, Trust-IT is going to be responsible for Data Management and is going to be **Data Controller**. The Data Processing Officer (DPO) for Trust-IT is: Mr. Michele Nannipieri, m.nannipieri@trust-it-services.com.

All other consortium partners (viz., COMMpla, TU DELFT, ICF, EAAE, and InnovaWood) will be **Data Processors**. This is needed for all partners to contribute to the specific objectives of the project, carrying out the various activities specified by the Grant Agreement with the needed efficiency and incremental value brought to the various datasets involved (e.g., the Community DB). To this aim, a **Data Processing Agreement (DPA)** will be signed by each Data Processor with the Data Controller. A copy of such an agreement is enclosed in Annex 1 to this document.

Each WP leader (with the technical qualification of Data Processor) is going to be responsible for data management within the WP, including updates and implementation of the DMP. The Project Coordinator (Trust-IT) assumes responsibility for overall data management and for evaluating the implementation of the DMP.

3.2. Deposition of data, documentation and code

Data collected directly on the website are stored on a relational database management system (RDBMS) MySQL. Drupal documentation and source code are available on www.drupal.org. The specific digiNEB.eu implementation includes a customised graphical theme which is stored on the Trust-IT servers.

The dataset collected internally, excluding data shared with external services (e.g. Youtube) are stored in Trust-IT servers hosting digineb.eu and located on Amazon AWS Cloud (EC2 instances), in the European region of Ireland.

The access to the AWS servers is restricted to COMMpla’s staff. The server architecture is described in the figure below.

Architecture on AWS

Figure 1 - Servers architecture for digiNEB.eu

3.3. Data access provided in case of restrictions

A limited number of project members have access to the system backend and they can access the information in any case where there are any restrictions. Data access is based on a manual administered RBAC (Role Based Access Control) process.

For the website (www.digineb.eu), main entry point for the data stored and used by the project, the open framework Drupal ([Drupal 9](#)) has been adopted to manage the content of the website. Natively, Drupal supports robust processes to manage access and availability in general in terms of authentication and authorisation to datasets. Access to the Drupal databases is limited only from the server machine where the database is installed and accessible as localhost as well, for security reasons.

The users accessing the data are given dedicated and customised privileges, dependent on their role, and the information is always on-line and available, when needed. The source data from any feedback forms undertaken is not made public or shared outside the consortium. It is only used by the consortium for the purposes of gathering feedback to help improve the platform for future activities.

3.4. Existing data being re-used

Some data entries are written as synopsis on a regular basis, and some data is being summarised from existing public reports of interest to the topics related to NEB community. In the case of curated reports, the source report is always referenced. The source data from surveys undertaken is not made public or shared outside the consortium.

When it is not concerned by the need of exploitation, the data will be aggregated and anonymised in order to have only data statistics without the detailed information regarding the source or any kind of personal information.

For progressing with the project, it is crucial to re-use the data collected to compare/aggregate or simply reach a final goal in the vision of digiNEB.eu project (see also Sec. 4.3 “FAIR data principles”).

Regarding the sharing of aggregated data forming the results of this project, whenever possible digiNEB.eu adopts the following licence for results: **Creative Commons attribution licence CC BY 4.0** for documents, reports, presentations, scientific publications (possibly in diamond open access outlets) etc., unless otherwise agreed amongst the partners for justified reasons. This allows sharing and adaptation of material as long as the work is appropriately attributed.

4. Data protection, FAIR principles, and ethical issues

Any personal data will be protected, pursuing Art. 15 of the Grant Agreement /2/. Moreover, the digiNEB.eu Consortium will implement FAIR principles, as described in the sections below. Finally, possible ethical issues will be hedged as described in Sec. 4.5 below.

Trust-IT implemented in the digiNEB.eu website a tool to show, inform and retrieve the consents in terms of Privacy Policy, Terms Of Use and Cookie usage that enable to recognise the anonymous visits of the website and the consents related to a registered user that is visiting the website. Each consents are stored via technical cookies in the browser of the visitors and for registered users, the consents are sent and stored to Trust-IT servers that collect all the agreement/rejection of a single user in order to be compliant with GDPR and an external audit as well.

4.1. Procedures implemented to ensure security and GDPR compliance

digiNEB.eu has a [Privacy Policy and Terms of Use Statement](#) , for services provided via the project website, which addresses personal data (processing, data subject's rights, opt-out, cookies used on the website and in social media, etc.). Trust-IT is the data controller regarding all personal data processing carried out through the Website, while all project partners have been identified as Data processors for GDPR purposes (see Sec. 3.1) and therefore they are allowed to access personal data provided via the digiNEB.eu website, managed by Trust-IT. For example, Name, contact details and other Personal Data (typically, email, sensitive information regarding gender, or dietary requirements needed for the organisation of events) processed for applications collected via the digiNEB.eu website will be kept by Trust-IT as Data Controller in terms of the GDPR for up to 5 years after project completion, also to allow for possible external audits, as requested by contractual provisions the Data Controller is subjected to.

The digiNEB.eu Consortium aims to strike a reasonable balance between security and convenience. Emails are usually sent as unencrypted text. If misrouted or intercepted, an unencrypted email could be read easily. Should a matter that requires **high security or confidentiality** be dealt with by the digiNEB.eu Consortium, Partners are requested to inform beforehand Trust-IT on the sensitivity of the information and they are requested not to send the related information through email. The Project will take measures to prevent data loss and facilitate any security aspects related to the transfer of data and information, as required, by adopting different information transmission protocols (e.g., sending, with a shared transfer, encrypted zip files that are password-protected).

The digiNEB.eu web platform adopts security measures consistent with the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to protect personal information under its control against loss, misuse, and alteration. In general terms, server configuration, https certificates, access controls, password storage and other relevant elements are dealt with in accordance with the provisions of the GDPR. The main points expressed by GDPR compliance are addressed in digiNEB.eu as indicated in the table below.

GDPR main points	digiNEB.eu solution to address the main point
The right to be informed	Privacy Policy and Terms of Use notice (available online at www.digineb.eu/privacy-policy)
The right of access	Each profile page shows the consents agreed by the user. Moreover, the user may access and change her/his Personal Data at any time.
The right to rectification	Each profile page permits at any time to change the consents agreed by the user and the correction or update of Personal Data where they may be inaccurate or incomplete

GDPR main points	digiNEB.eu solution to address the main point
The right to erasure	The user may delete her/his own account including the personal data involved
The right to restrict processing	The user can request the restriction of the processing of her/his Personal Data, where she/he feels that the Personal Data processed is inaccurate, unnecessary or unlawfully processed, or where she/he has objected to the processing.
The right to data portability	It is possible to provide data export in CSV format
The right to object	Objection is possible and can be exerted by the user at any point in time. In the privacy notice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individuals are informed of their right to object “at the point of first communication” (namely, in the privacy notice).. This is “explicitly brought to the attention of the data subject” and is “presented clearly and separately from any other information” (namely, in the privacy notice).
Rights related to automated decision making and profiling	Usually no automated processing of personal data on Drupal
Accountability and governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appropriate technical and organisational measures that ensure and demonstrate that digiNEB.eu complies have been implemented. These include internal data protection policies such as staff training, internal audits of processing activities, and reviews of internal HR policies. Relevant documentation on processing activities is maintained in the campaign activities that are carried out. Trust-IT has appointed a DPO (see Sec. 3.1). Measures that meet the principles of data protection by design and data protection by default have been implemented following the 7 step methodology suggested by the Norwegian Data Protection Authority /4/ as a best practice to address Art. 25 of the GDPR. In particular, for step 4, “coding”, the use of Drupal provides a strong foundation of ‘security-by-design’ principles. Security features will be improved on the future releases of the digiNEB.eu platform and, if needed, on an ongoing basis.
Breach notification	<p>The Data Controller shall notify the relevant supervisory authority of a breach where it is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals. In case of data breach, the notification will be sent within 72 hours to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The Italian national authority (Garante per la protezione dei dati personali - www.garanteprivacy.it, piazza Venezia, 11 - Roma). Commission de la protection de la vie privée (https://www.privacycommission.be/fr/politique-vie-privee-et-disclaimer), Rue de la Presse, 35, 1000 Bruxelles. <p>Additionally, the EC and the digiNEB.eu Data Processors will be informed.</p>

Table 2 - GDPR main points

4.2. Cookies

The digiNEB.eu website, to be compliant with the GDPR law in terms of Cookies, shows all the information on cookies that are being used and exploited, presenting the end-user the choices she/he is entitled to. There are some **technical cookies** that are strictly necessary for the navigation of the website and their use cannot be rejected. In case the end-user disagrees with them, she/he will not be allowed to properly navigate the digiNEB.eu website.

digiNEB.eu is using **measurement cookies** provided by Google Analytics and in the specific for the Google Tag Manager. These cookies can be deactivated by the end-user and the navigation is going to be not seen by Google Analytics. The reason for these cookies is that usage of these types of data is

extremely useful to conduct quantitative research in order to disseminate project results and to reach out to target stakeholders with personalised messages and quality information.

The digiNEB.eu website also uses **third-party cookies** – i.e. cookies from websites / web servers other than digiNEB.eu's. These third parties will either act as independent data controllers regarding their own cookies (using the data they collect for their own purposes and under terms defined by them, e.g. Instagram) or as data processors for Trust-IT srl (processing personal data on Trust-IT srl's behalf, e.g. MailChimp). For further information on how these third parties may use your information, please refer to their privacy policies:

- Instagram
- LinkedIn
- MailChimp
- Twitter
- Youtube

4.3. FAIR data principles

In the sections below, the main elements supporting the FAIR data principles that will be put in place by digiNEB.eu are outlined.

4.3.1 Making data findable

Discoverability of Data

The digiNEB.eu web platform has been designed to allow the users to upload and modify the information that directly concerns them, when they have logged into the system. Their level of discoverability is tailored and dependent on their privileges as a user, in that, once logged in, they will have access to their own profiles and access to the current status of the information they published (e.g., in the TWGs, in the Early Adopters sections) .

Approach towards Search Keywords

The digineb.eu website is equipped with a search functionality that is mostly used to find content more easily (based on Drupal's native functionalities).

Approach for clear versioning

The TWGs entries are date and time stamped, which will enable clear time positioning of the entries themselves and reports can be generated, when needed (e.g. for purposes of gathering anonymised statistics, as required by the project).

4.3.2 Making data openly accessible

Data openly available

The textual and graphical data entered by the end users into the digineb.eu web platform in relation to the TWGs, digital toolkit, success stories, Early Adopters and the NEB Observatory in general are meant to be publicly available, their main scope being the one of dissemination of the digital solutions as per the digiNEB.eu mission profile. Personal data on the community of users are normally not disclosed and they are only made publicly available upon explicit consent from the individuals themselves.

Methods or Software Tools to Access Data

The digiNEB.eu platform has been developed using Drupal, a powerful CMS (Content management system), that allows a modern look and an appealing UX design. This platform was chosen since it has standard features that are functional and easy to use, such as content authoring, reliable performance, and excellent security. The Drupal Platform (made in PHP language) was found to be extremely flexible and modular, necessary for the purposes of the digiNEB.eu platform. The entire platform is designed with a user-centric layout to facilitate access to the content and usability of the portal. Finally, the Drupal platform is a well-suited base to interface with a GDPR-compliant platform for fora (TWGs), namely FLARUM (<https://flarum.org/>), which is one of the central functionalities provided by the digiNEB.eu initiative. A FLARUM instance, dedicated for digiNEB.eu project, has been set up on Trust-IT's infrastructure, based on AWS. All the security best practices have been considered as the hosting and monitoring of the digiNEB.eu website.

4.3.3 Making Data findable, including provisions of metadata

Assess the Interoperability of Data

The data from the digiNEB.eu web platform will not be shared with third parties for any reason, except for our own anonymous statistical data. Therefore, the interoperability aspects of the data are not considered by the project.

Standard vocabulary for all data types

During the data entry process, the project team provides guidance to the users for data entry in the various webforms (e.g. for collecting info on success stories) in terms of standard vocabulary and size of entries (number of characters or words) for all data types.

4.3.4 Increasing data re-use

Data permitted to the broadest reuse possible

When users register, they accept terms and conditions where it is made clear that data added to the platform in the Success Cases, TWGs, Early Adopters, and Digital Toolkit sections will be made publicly available and therefore natively re-usable (see Table 1 for data format and other details).

Data Quality assurance processes

The PMB which is composed of members from each consortium partner of digiNEB.eu and whose responsibilities includes all aspects regarding formalisation of all project decisions, will monitor on data management also with the important consideration in mind to ensure that the quality of the data is taken into consideration.

Length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

From the perspective of open data available for re-use, no time limit will be put on data availability for information that will be published on the digiNEB.eu website. Be that as it may, it is expected that the data will remain re-usable for the lifetime of this project and at least another 5 years after project completion, as per the EC requests. It is hereby expressly agreed that personal data will be re-usable also after completion of digiNEB.eu, but only within the scope of the NEB initiative.

4.4. Ethical issues

As indicated in Sec. 2, the project involves the collection of personal data and personal opinions from human participants as the online portal of digiNEB.eu envisages such functionalities and processes. While we consider that ethical approvals may not be needed, we agree that the project is not free of

ethical considerations, especially considering the open discussions that will take place in the TWGs and in the workshops. While confirming that all discussions in the TWGs and in the workshops will be supervised and a formal moderator will be assigned before any content and personal opinion expressed by the participants to the discussions is published on the TWG (and on post-events report generated from workshops) hosted @ www.digineb.eu, we identify the following, according to the ethics Horizon Europe Programme Guidance on ethics self-assessment in HE:

1) Confirm that informed consent has been obtained - the consent is obtained when the user registers to the website and agrees to the privacy policy. Item number 1 of the Privacy Policy is related to informed consent (see Appendix 1, Privacy Policy). Consent for any information that will be made open access will also be obtained.

2) Documents to be provided/kept on file: all records are kept on the web platform' server, and can be inspected, if requested.

We will continue to liaise with the Institutional Ethics Committee to ensure that we are fully compliant with regulatory and legal requirements and submit a full application for ethical review, if required, in line with their terms of reference.

Concerning all datasets other than the ones related to the TWGs and Workshops, no ethical issues are envisaged (see also Table 1 in Sec. 2).

5. Allocation of resources for data management

The overall volume of data that will be archived and published is estimated to be less than 50 GB. A revised estimate will be made at least every 6 months, to allocate the correct resources.

Delivering data that is as FAIR as possible is an integral part of the project strategy and no separate step or budget for maintenance of such qualities has been planned. The costs associated with the data is considered low, as the system has already been designed as GDPR compliant and uses tools that are both user friendly and provide the developers with ease of access for moderation. The efforts associated with ensuring the data is FAIR is taken care of primarily in the personnel costs of the project. Be that as it may, the amount of research data envisaged for the project is modest and does not require a cost-benefit analysis for the long-term storage of each component. The solution for long-term preservation - intended in excess of 10 years, hence “indefinite” in practical terms - will be discussed during the lifetime of the digiNEB.eu project and inserted in this section of the document.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable sets out the main processes and procedures that will be followed for data management in the Project.

The pivotal decisions made concerning data management are:

- Trust-IT is going to be the Data Controller and all the other partners (viz. TU DELFT, COMMpla, ICF, EAAE, and IW) are going to be the Data Processors. A DPA, provided in Annex 1 to this document, is going to be put in place.
- Data processes & procedures have been designed to be natively GDPR-compliant.
- FAIR data principles are followed by the digiNEB.eu Consortium.
- Ethical issues are not envisaged, the TWGs being the area to be closely monitored to avoid any of those issues.

It is agreed among all Project Partners that this document will be updated whenever changes are made to any of the topics described herein.

7. References

/1/ D1.1 'Project Handbook", the digiNEB.eu Consortium, December 2022.

/2/ Grant Agreement, project 101083743 - digiNEB.eu; EC DG CONNECT, Digital Europe Programme, DIGITAL-2021-DEPLOY-01, 24 November 2022.

/3/ [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR, Regulation EU 2016/679).

/4/ Datatilsynet - Norwegian Data Protection Agency: "Software development with Data Protection by Design and by Default" - <https://www.datatilsynet.no/en/about-privacy/virksomhetenes-plikter/innebygd-personvern/data-protection-by-design-and-by-default/?print=true>

Annex 1 “Data Processing Agreement (DPA)”

DPA to be signed by Trust-IT (Data Controller of digiNEB.eu) with each of the Data Processors.

Data Processing Agreement (DPA) – project digiNEB.eu

Processing of personal data in the digiNEB.eu platform of the Project **digiNEB.eu** (Grant Agreement no. 101083743, hereafter ‘the Project’) shall comply with the legal framework on data protection, i.e.: **Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – ‘the GDPR’^[1])** as concerns personal data processing by the selected contractor in execution of the Project with Trust-IT Srl, a company headquartered in Via Francesco Redi 10 – 56124 Pisa (Italy), VAT no. 01870130505 (hereafter, **DATACONTROLLER**), represented by its Data Protection Officer, Michele Nannipieri.

In the framework of the Project, **DATACONTROLLER** is the **Data Controller** under this Regulation and the organisation **XXXXXX, a company headquartered in FULL ADDRESS HERE, VAT no. XXXXXXXXXXXX** (hereafter, **DATAPROCESSOR**), represented by its **XXXXXX XXXXXXXX, NAME SURNAME**, is the **Data Processor**. The processor shall act only under the instructions of **DATACONTROLLER**.

Agree	Data protection requirement
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal data processing in execution of the Project, where DATACONTROLLER and DATAPROCESSOR are involved, shall comply with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (the GDPR). The digiNEB.eu document titled “D1.2 Data Management Plan” is the reference document for this purpose.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The processing of personal data shall happen in accordance with Article 29 of the GDPR.
<input type="checkbox"/>	To process the personal data only on instructions agreed upon with DATACONTROLLER , in particular with regard to the purposes of the processing, the categories of data that may be processed, the recipients of the data and the means by which the data subject may exercise its rights.
<input type="checkbox"/>	To ensure that access to personal data is granted to the extent strictly necessary for the implementation of the Project and to ensure that persons authorised to process the personal data have committed themselves to confidentiality.
<input type="checkbox"/>	To implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risks, in particular the risk of accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to the personal data, processed or stored.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Not to engage another processor of personal data (i.e. by means of a subcontract), without prior written authorisation of DATACONTROLLER . Where another processor is engaged for carrying out specific processing activities on the personal data, the same data protection obligations as set out in the contract shall be imposed on the other processor.
<input type="checkbox"/>	To assist DATACONTROLLER in the fulfilment of the controller’s obligation to respond to requests for exercising the data subject’s rights laid down in Chapter III of the GDPR.
<input type="checkbox"/>	To assist DATACONTROLLER with its obligations with regard to security of processing, the notification obligations in case of a personal data breach, as well as where applicable

	cooperation in data protection impact assessments (DPIAs) and prior consultations with the Supervisory Authority, outlined in Art. 33 to 40 of the GDPR.
<input type="checkbox"/>	To make available to DATACONTROLLER all information to demonstrate compliance with the obligations laid down in the GDPR and to allow for and to contribute to audits, including inspections, conducted by DATACONTROLLER or another auditor mandated by DATACONTROLLER .
Agree	Data protection requirement concerning localisation of and access to the personal data
<input type="checkbox"/>	The personal data submitted to the digiNEB.eu platform are collected in compliance with the GDPR and shall only be processed and held in data centres within the territory of the European Union and the European Economic Area and will not leave that territory. This includes also any backup centres and location of backup data. DATAPROCESSOR agrees to ensure to the best of its ability that its use of the personal data so held shall also only occur within that territory.
<input type="checkbox"/>	DATAPROCESSOR may not change the location of data processing without the prior written authorisation of DATACONTROLLER .
<input type="checkbox"/>	DATAPROCESSOR shall inform DATACONTROLLER in case of any need for transfer of personal data to third countries or international organisations and will perform such transfer only after written authorisation by DATACONTROLLER . Any transfer of personal data to third countries or international organisations shall fully comply with the requirements laid down in Chapter V of the GDPR.
<input type="checkbox"/>	DATAPROCESSOR shall notify DATACONTROLLER without delay of any legally binding request for disclosure of the personal data processed on behalf of DATACONTROLLER made to DATAPROCESSOR (or to any of its subcontractors) by any national public authority, including an authority from a third country. DATAPROCESSOR may not give such access without the prior written authorisation of DATACONTROLLER .
<input type="checkbox"/>	To contact the Data Protection Officer (DPO) of DATACONTROLLER , in charge of monitoring data protection compliance, with any questions arising or in case of need for assistance concerning personal data protection at the address: privacy@digineb.eu .

Date: **DD.MM.2023**

For Trust-IT Srl, **DATACONTROLLER**:

For **XXXXXXX**, **DATAPROCESSOR**

DPO

NAME SURNAME
ROLE

[1] Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ L 119, 4.5.2016.